

Eurodoc Code of Conduct

Purpose of this Document

In order to promote an inclusive and healthy organisational culture, the Administrative Board of 2023/2024 initiated the work of introducing a code of conduct for the volunteers in Eurodoc in line with Eurodoc's vision, mission, and core values. This work was finalised by the Administrative Board of 2024/2025. The Administrative Board is responsible for the association's culture, including an annual review of Eurodoc's Code of Conduct in consultation with its members and employees. Eurodoc shares this document with all associations and individuals that are expected to comply with Eurodoc's values, vision, mission, and code of conduct.

Eurodoc's Mission and Vision

Eurodoc's vision: "A fair and sustainable research culture where early career researchers are treated with respect and have access to long-term and stable career pathways."

Eurodoc's mission: "To advocate for positive change in the policies, culture and environment that affect the quality of training, well-being and employment conditions of early career researchers."

Core Values

Democratic consensus-building: Eurodoc ensures the democratic nature of all internal processes and strives for consensus. This means that Eurodoc strives to meet the interests of all its members and seeks broad agreement. It thereby aspires to set an example of democratic consensus-building for other actors.

Mutual respect: Eurodoc's culture is centred on mutual respect of each other's capabilities, skills, aspirations, and work capacities. This includes mutual help in the development of tasks and collaboration for the achievement of common goals.

Professionalism: Eurodoc aims for producing high-quality work in the various activities it undertakes. These should be conducted with diligence as well as in consultation with and carried out by the colleagues best suited for the tasks. Eurodoc's professionalism relies on good communication with stakeholders in higher education and being a reliable partner for them. Ensuring professionalism, while recognising that much of Eurodoc's work is conducted by volunteers, requires setting priorities.

Transparency: Eurodoc ensures equal access to information and processes for all of its member organisations and communicates its internal mechanisms, decision-making processes, and decisions to them.

Equality and Equity: Equality and equity are core values of Eurodoc, they are fostered by keeping entry thresholds low. Eurodoc strives to set an example for young researchers and other actors in higher education.

Diversity: Eurodoc values diversity of opinions, backgrounds, experiences, and identities. It is recognized as a crucial asset to the work of Eurodoc that must be respected and nurtured.

Inclusiveness: No individual should be treated differently on the basis of gender, gender identity or expression, ethnicity, religion, disability, sexual orientation, or age. Harassment in any form will not be tolerated. Eurodoc ensures that individuals involved in its work can contribute regardless of academic status, discipline, research topic, country of origin or affiliation.

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Eurodoc's daily activity is based on participative democracy and our decision-making aims to constructively build consensus. All members have an equal right to contribute to Eurodoc's activity and must be given a fair opportunity to do so. Therefore, organisational structure and decision-making processes must be made transparent for all involved.

Eurodoc is an organisation run by volunteers. Eurodoc acknowledges that volunteer contributions to its mission and vision come in a multitude of ways. We endeavour to support one another and be respectful of each other's contributions. We wish to build an organisation that encourages people to contribute in a manner in which they are comfortable, in particular this means being mindful of each other's time and capacity limits.

Eurodoc has limited structural funding and therefore does not have the possibility to use financial resources for its core operations. We thus prioritise the projects we take on based on their importance for our mission and vision and based on where we think the greatest impact for improving the careers and conditions of early career researchers can be achieved.

National Associations' Responsibilities as Members of Eurodoc

National Associations are responsible for their own actions. As a member of Eurodoc, they bridge the gap between ECRs in their countries and policy-making at the European level. When **acting in their capacity as a member of Eurodoc**, they shall adhere to Eurodoc's Statutes, Internal Regulation, and this Code of Conduct. In their capacity as members of Eurodoc, National Associations shall furthermore comply with the following:

- Designate their delegates to Eurodoc in a manner that ensures fairness, non-discrimination, and equity.
- Refrain from providing false or misleading information in relation to Eurodoc, its staff, other volunteers, or partners.
- Ensure mutual respect and courtesy and in particular respect and acknowledge the volunteer nature of Eurodoc's work.
- Ensure that their delegates to Eurodoc when acting in their capacity as NA delegates to Eurodoc
 - act in accordance with the core values outlined in this document;
 - pass on all relevant information to their NA and its members, as well from their NAs and its members to Eurodoc;
 - do not share internal or confidential information and documents outside of the NA's decision making body.

Responsibilities of Individuals acting within or on behalf of Eurodoc

This pertains to: Administrative board members, employees, advisory board members, members of the secretariat, coordinators and members of working groups and task forces, representatives mandated by Eurodoc, auditors, procurators, NA delegates when acting in their capacity as NA delegates to Eurodoc, as well as any other individual acting on behalf of Eurodoc.

Individuals are responsible for their own actions. When acting in **relation to or on behalf of** Eurodoc, they shall comply with the following principles:

- Uphold Eurodoc's vision, mission, and core values.
- Act ethically and with honesty and integrity.
- Make decisions that are fair and equitable and acknowledge others' contributions.
- Treat everyone with respect, courtesy, and dignity.

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- Refrain from discriminatory behaviour or harassment based on (non-exclusive list) age, gender, sexuality, nationality, religion, heritages, or marital status.
- Respect the boundaries between personal and professional lives and respect others' work capacities, in particular for volunteer contributions.
- Ensure they act on a basis of consent in particular when it comes to
 - the sharing of images, pictures, and other materials from Eurodoc meetings and events;
 - the sharing of confidential information pertaining to Eurodoc or its members;
 - the collection and the sharing of other person's personal data in the context of Eurodoc.
- Refrain from providing false or misleading information in relation to Eurodoc, its staff, other volunteers, or partners.

Responsibilities of the Administration of Eurodoc

This pertains to: Administrative board members, members of the secretariat elected by the annual general meeting or appointed by the administrative board, advisory board members, and the procurator.

The Administration's core responsibility is to ensure Eurodoc's continuation, the sustainability of its work for the individuals involved, and to carry out Eurodoc's mission in order to actualise its vision. The interests of Eurodoc – as described in its statutes and internal regulations – cannot be subsumed by the interests of any individual or subgroup listed above.

Eurodoc has a number of core tasks that are essential for the continuous functioning of the organisation. These are outlined by the statutes and need to be prioritised by the Administration of Eurodoc above other tasks and include: the organisation of the annual general meeting, the fulfilment of regulatory requirements to ensure the continuation of the organisation, the organisation of regular board meetings, the completion of accounting and bookkeeping, the fulfilment of contractual obligations.

The Administration furthermore shall always

- uphold the Eurodoc's vision, mission, and core values,
- comply with all relevant legislation, standards, and other compliance mechanisms,
- strive to set an example for good practices of organisational work, and
- avoid conflict of interests. If a conflict of interest arises, this should be communicated to the board of Eurodoc in a timely and transparent manner. The board of Eurodoc will then make a decision on how to proceed.

Because of the nature of its volunteer work, the Administration of Eurodoc shall

- ensure the well-being of its members and the sustainability of the work for the individuals,
- always acknowledge the work of every person who contributes, and
- only employ individuals if a decent salary and decent employment conditions can be ensured.

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

